

Oral presentation proposal for the Manouba symposium 16 to 19 June 2021

Title: Using hypnosis in competition period to enhance self-confidence and to reduce anxiety among volleyball players

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Objectives

The aim of our research was to test the influence of hypnosis on the evolution of self-confidence and anxiety.

Method

Our sample included (N = 7 volleyball players) of a Tunisian Volleyball Team, aged 16 to 24, were followed daily for four weeks to enjoy their training and followed a program practicing the use of hypnosis. To assess the evolution of the psychological variables, participants completed the following questionnaire based on three measurement times (at the beginning of the experiment, after two weeks and at the end of the four weeks): The Competitive State Anxiety Inventory-2 (CSAI-2).

Result

The questionnaire (CSAI-2) was obtained statistically significant from the three times analysis of variance (Alpha = .78). A one-way model ANOVA revealed that hypnosis improved for the athletes ($p < .01$); self-confidence increased ($p < .01$) and cognitive anxiety decreased ($p < .05$). Correlation analysis revealed that changes in hypnosis were moderately related to changes in self-confidence ($p < .05$).

Conclusion

The results of the study showed that hypnosis can enhance self-confidence and reduce cognitive anxiety. These observations allow us to guide future interventions with athletes to strengthen them psychologically. Recent studies have demonstrated the links between personality and hypnotizability using the "Hypnotic Induction Profile " (HIP).

In these studies a positive bivariate correlation between extroversion and hypnotizability was shown ($r = .35$, $p = .03$), while Type D personality (Social Inhibition and Negative Effect) was negatively associated with hypnotizability ($r = -.44$, $p = .004$).

Parallel to this finding, a study on the operationalize of mental skills in the area of mental preparation in sport demonstrated the importance of the goal setting (basic skills), relaxation (psychosomatic skills), mental imagery and mental practice (cognitive skills) (Hamrouni, Alem, Baert, & Bouguerra, 2015). Indeed, these athletes can be referred to as operational as opposed to circumstantial. Operational are task-focused, resulting in better decision-making (projects, task forces).

Key words: hypnosis, self-confident, anxiety...

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